

AN ELECTROMAGNETIC PULSE PROOF VEHICLE

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Abstract—An electromagnetic pulse (EMP) is a powerful burst of electromagnetic radiation that can be generated by a high-altitude nuclear explosion or a non-nuclear device. In our modern world, cars are equipped with a wide range of sophisticated electronics, making them highly vulnerable to the destructive effects of an EMP strike. When an EMP occurs, it releases surges of current that can wreak havoc on the delicate circuits and chips found in these electronic systems.

The sources of EMP radiation are diverse, with nuclear explosions and lightning strikes being the most common. In the case of a deliberate EMP attack, the consequences could be catastrophic. An EMP strike would result in the destruction of electronics and digital circuitry in the affected area, leading to a widespread loss of electric power. This would have a devastating impact on our homes, businesses, and even our military infrastructure.

To mitigate the potentially disastrous effects of an EMP attack, EMP shields have been developed. These shields provide surge protection by preemptively disabling electrical systems, preventing the destructive currents from causing irreversible damage. By employing advanced technology, EMP shields can detect and neutralize the incoming electromagnetic radiation, safeguarding vital electronics.

Given the increasing reliance on technology in our daily lives, an EMP attack has the potential to cripple our society. It would disrupt communication systems, transportation networks, and financial institutions, causing widespread chaos and severely impeding emergency response efforts. Thus, investing in EMP protection measures becomes crucial for both individuals and institutions, ensuring the resilience of our critical infrastructure and maintaining our way of life in the face of such a threat.

Index Terms—Electro Magnetic Pulse, Faraday's Cage, EMP, High voltage generator

I. INTRODUCTION

An electromagnetic pulse (EMP), also sometimes called a transient electromagnetic disturbance, is a short burst of electromagnetic energy. Such a pulse's origin may be a natural occurrence or human-made and can occur as a radiated, electric, or magnetic field or a conducted electric current, depending on the source. EMP interference is generally disruptive or damaging to electronic equipment, and at higher energy levels a powerful EMP event such as a lightning strike can damage physical objects such as buildings and aircraft structures.

An electromagnetic pulse (EMP) attack refers to the intentional release of a high-intensity burst of electromagnetic energy that can disrupt or destroy electronic systems and infrastructure. EMP attacks can be conducted through various means, such as nuclear detonations, non-nuclear weapons, or even natural phenomena like solar flares. The effects of an EMP can be wide-ranging and devastating, impacting critical infrastructures, communication networks, transportation systems, and the overall functioning of modern society.

The management of EMP effects is an important branch of electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) engineering. Weapons have been developed to deliver the damaging effects of high-energy EMP. According to research from the United States Department of Homeland Security, EMP weapons have the potential to disrupt unprotected critical infrastructure within the United States and could impact millions over large parts of the country. There is concern about the EMP threat, but no accurate prediction on how many people will face massive damages from this attack.

According to research from Martin and Mathew Weiss, of the scenarios that might lead to electrical network collapse, EMP has received the widest public attention. The threat possibility of an EMP attack has grown more as a possibility than it did in the past, when it was not seen as an incoming threat to the United States. An electromagnetic pulse is a short surge of electromagnetic energy. Its short duration means that it will be spread over a range of frequencies.

EMP attacks typically produce three distinct pulse components: E1, E2, and E3. The E1 component is a high-frequency pulse that can damage or destroy electronic devices by inducing high voltages. It primarily affects small electronic systems and is characterized by its rapid onset and short duration. The E2 component is a slower pulse that can affect a wider range of electronics, including power grids and communication systems. Lastly, the E3 component is a long-lasting pulse caused by geomagnetic disturbances and can induce damaging currents in long conductors, such as power lines.

MODES OF ENERGY TRANSFER

- A. The mode of energy transfer (radiated, electric, magnetic or conducted).
- B. The range or spectrum of frequencies present.

C. Pulse waveform: shape, duration and amplitude.

D. The last two of these, the frequency spectrum and the pulse waveform, are interrelated via the Fourier transform which describes how component waveforms may sum to the observed frequency spectrum.

The impact of an EMP attack can vary depending on the altitude of the burst, the yield of the weapon, and the vulnerability of the targeted systems. A high-altitude burst, known as a high-altitude EMP (HEMP), can generate a widespread and potent electromagnetic field that covers a large geographic area, affecting multiple systems simultaneously. In contrast, a localized attack targeting specific infrastructure or military installations can result in more targeted disruptions.

The consequences of an EMP attack can be severe. The immediate effect is the disruption or destruction of electronic devices, including computers, communication equipment, power grids, and transportation systems. This can lead to a breakdown in critical services, such as electricity, water supply, transportation networks, and emergency services. The long-term consequences can include societal unrest, economic instability, and a prolonged recovery period.

Protecting against EMP attacks requires a multi-faceted approach. Hardening critical infrastructure and military systems to withstand the effects of EMP is one strategy. This involves shielding electronic components, implementing surge protection measures, and using robust grounding techniques. Additionally, redundancy and backup systems can help ensure continuity of essential services.

Addressing the threat of EMP attacks also requires international cooperation, intelligence sharing, and the development of defensive and offensive capabilities. Governments and organizations need to invest in research and development to better understand EMP phenomena, improve protective measures, and develop effective countermeasures.

1.1 Background:

Types of EMP:

“An EMP arises where the source emits a short-duration pulse of energy. The energy is usually broadband by nature, although it often excites a relatively narrow-band damped sine wave response in the surrounding environment. Some types are generated as repetitive and regular pulse trains.” Different types of EMP arise from natural, man-made, and weapons effects.

Types of natural EMP event includes:

Lightning electromagnetic pulse (LEMP) The discharge is typically an initial huge current flow, at least mega-amps, followed by a train of pulses of decreasing energy.

Electrostatic discharge (ESD), “as a result of two charged objects coming into proximity or even contact.

Meteoritic EMP. The discharge of electromagnetic energy resulting from either the impact of a meteoroid with a spacecraft or the explosive breakup of a meteoroid passing through the Earth's atmosphere.

Coronal mass ejection (CME), “sometimes referred to as a solar EMP. A burst of plasma and accompanying magnetic field, ejected from the solar corona, and released into the solar wind”.

Types of (civil) man-made EMP event include:

- Switching action of electrical circuitry, whether isolated or repetitive (as a pulse train).
 - Electric motors can create a train of pulses as the internal electrical contacts make and break connections as the armature rotates.
 - Gasoline engine ignition systems can create a train of pulses as the spark plugs are energized or fired.
- Continual switching actions of digital electronic circuitry.
 - Power line surges. These can be up to several kilovolts, enough to damage electronic equipment that is insufficiently protected.

Types of military EMP include:

- Nuclear electromagnetic pulse (NEMP), as a result of a nuclear explosion. A variant of this is the high altitude nuclear.
- EMP (HEMP), which produces a secondary pulse due to particle interactions with the Earth's atmosphere and magnetic field.
- Non-nuclear electromagnetic pulse (NNEMP) weapons.

In conclusion, EMP attacks pose a significant threat to modern society by targeting electronic systems and infrastructure. The disruptive potential of EMPs can lead to widespread damage, social chaos, and long-term consequences. By implementing protective measures, enhancing resilience, and promoting international collaboration, we can mitigate the risks posed by EMP attacks and safeguard critical systems against such threats.

II. REFERENCE PAPERS BRIEF DESCRIPTION

- 1. “Your car will probably be fine after an EMP”. Jon Stokes. The Prepared. Published: 23rd November 2020 [Ref**

No.11

Rezvani motor manufactures the Rezvani Tank X 2020. This is a very sophisticated tank vehicle with wholesome features; where military meets luxury. This bulletproof tank is a 1000 HP beast which comes with features like radar, EMP protection, ballistics armor, Evasion tools, Thermal night vision and a lot more. B7-rated glass armor and level 7 ballistic protection. Rezvani clocks the Tank to 60 miles per hour in about six seconds flat. It looks very much like the Jeep wrangler. Cars nowadays are equipped with suite of sophisticated electronics. An electro-magnetic pulse (EMP) strike can create surges of current inside electronics and destroy the circuits and chips. Common sources of EMP radiation include nuclear explosion or lightning strikes. EMP shields provide surge protection by disabling the electrical systems prior to an attack. The EMP shield in the Tank X uses radioactively charged gases to shed strikes of electricity in 500 trillionths of a second.

2. “US Air Force is guarding against electromagnetic pulse attacks. Should we worry?” EddGent, Live Science, Published:11th March 2021 [Ref No.2]

The U.S. military has a “cruise missile carrying an EMP generator.” The technology required to protect against EMPs is similar to what is already used to prevent damage from power surges caused by lightning, Pry said. The military primarily uses a simple Faraday Cage to protect their equipment against the potential damages of an EMP attack. During a surge of electromagnetic energy, such as the most severe EMPs, military equipment is protected from damage by this simple Faraday Cage.

3. “New sensors for measuring very short electromagnetic pulses”. H.-M. Shen, R.W.P. King, T.T. Wu, IEEE, Published: 6th June 1990, Electronic ISSN: 1558-2221 [Ref No.3]

In order to detect very short electromagnetic pulses under 100ps in width, a wide-band receiving antenna with a bandwidth from 0 to 14 GHz is needed. The usual short dipoles or monopoles do not provide both the required fidelity (bandwidth) and sensitivity. A novel type of electromagnetic pulse (EMP) sensor has been designed, analyzed, and tested. It is simple, inexpensive, and can detect the electromagnetic pulse with both high fidelity and high sensitivity. An approximate analysis is given for better understanding and optimum design of the proposed EMP antenna.

INSPEC Accession Number: 3734784

4. “Report of the Commission to Assess the Threat to the United States from Electromagnetic Pulse (EMP) Attack”, U.S. Congress, Published: 2008 [Ref No.4]

NATURE OF THE EMP THREAT

The detonation of a nuclear bomb at altitudes ranging from 40 to 400 kilometers above the Earth's surface causes high-altitude EMP. EMP causes instantaneous disruption and damage to electronic equipment and electrical infrastructure. In the parameter range of current interest, EMP has not been recorded in the scientific literature to have direct impacts on individuals.

In 1962, EMP and its effects were observed during US and Soviet atmospheric test programs. Figure 1 illustrates the Starfish nuclear detonation, which was not planned or constructed to be an EMP generator, at an altitude of roughly 400 km over Johnston Island in the Pacific Ocean.

Some electronic and electrical systems in the Hawaiian Islands, 1400 km away, were damaged, causing street-lighting systems to fail, circuit breakers to trip, burglar alarms to sound, and damage to a telecommunications relay station. The Soviets conducted a series of nuclear tests that year, exploding 300 kiloton warheads about 300, 150, and 60 kilometres over their test site in South Central Asia.

They claim that each shot caused damage to above and underground buried wires across 600 km. Surge arrester burnout, spark-gap failure, blown fuses, and power supply problems were also detected. An EMP strike is significant because one or a few high-altitude nuclear detonations can create EMP effects that might possibly disrupt or destroy electronic and electrical systems across most of the United States almost simultaneously, at a time set by an opponent.

Gamma rays from a high-altitude nuclear detonation interact with the atmosphere to produce a radio-frequency wave of unique, spatially varying intensity that covers everything within line-of-sight of the explosion's center point. It is useful to focus on three major EMP components.

Widespread red air glow (6300 Å) amid dark clouds, caused mostly by x-ray-excited atomic oxygen (i.e., oxygen by photoelectrons liberated by Starfish X-rays)

Figure 1. Starfish Nuclear Detonation

FIRST EMP COMPONENT (E1):

The first component is a free-field energy pulse with a rising time calculated in the billionths to billionths of a second range. The "electromagnetic shock" is responsible for the disruption or damage of electronics-based control systems, sensors, communication systems, protection systems, computers, and similar equipment. As seen in Figure 2, its destruction or functional disruption occurs virtually simultaneously over a very broad region.

Figure 2. Illustrative EMP Effects – Fast Pulse

SECOND EMP COMPONENT (E2):

The middle-time component spans nearly the same geographic region as the first component and has a time-dependence comparable to lightning, but its nature is significantly more geographically extensive and has a little lower amplitude. In general, it would not be a problem for critical infrastructure systems because they already have preventative mechanisms in place to defend against lightning strikes. The most severe danger is synergistic, because the E2 component follows the first component's insult by a fraction of a second, which can impair or eliminate several protective and regulatory functions. As a result, the energy associated with the second component may be permitted to enter and harm systems.

THIRD EMP COMPONENT (E3):

A following, slower-rising, longer-duration pulse causes disruptive currents in long electricity transmission lines, causing damage to electrical supply and distribution systems connected to suchlines (Figure 3). The sequencing of EMP components E1, E2, and E3 is crucial since each can produce harm, and subsequent damage might be exacerbated as a result of earlier damage. The region subjected to the EMP incident contains over 70% of the entire electrical power load in the United States.

5. “The Early-Time (E1) High-Altitude Electromagnetic Pulse (HEMP) and Its Impact onthe U.S. Power Grid”, Edward Savage, James Gilbert, William Radasky, Metatech Corporation, Published: January 2010. [Ref No.5]

This report describes the threat of the early-time (E1) high-altitude electromagnetic pulse (HEMP)produced by nuclear detonations above an altitude of ~30 km. The report describes the mechanismsthat create the E1 HEMP, the evidence for concern about this threat, and how it can impact the U.S. power grid. As the late-time (E3) part of the HEMP is considerably different in its frequencycontent and how it affects the power grid, this aspect will be discussed in another report.

6. “National Co-ordinating Centre for Communications (NCC), “Electromagnetic Pulse (EMP) Protection and Resilience Guidelines for Critical Infrastructure and Equipment”, Version 2.2, 05-02-2019.”, Dr. George H. Baker, Dr. Radasky, Dr. James L. Gilbert, Published: 5th February 2019 [Ref No.6]

"The United States' critical national infrastructure faces a present and continuing existential threatfrom combined-arms warfare, including cyber and manmade electromagnetic pulse (EMP) attack,as well as natural EMP from a solar superstorm." During the Cold War, the United States was primarily concerned with an EMP attack generated bya high-altitude nuclear weapon as a tactic by which the Soviet Union could undermine the UnitedStates' national command authority and ability to respond to a nuclear attack—thus negating the deterrence value of assured nuclear retaliation. Over the last decade, newly armed enemies, such as North Korea, have developed the capability and threatened to launch an EMP assault on the United States.

III. DESIGN AND METHODOLOGIES

3.1 Block Diagram

Figure 3. Block Diagram (System Hardware Architecture)

Description (Hardware Architecture of the Project)

- Battery: It is used to provide power supply to the circuitry.
- Switch: To regulate the turning ON and OFF the circuit.
- High Voltage Generator: It is used to generate high voltage surge between spark gap.
- Coil: It is responsible for generation of Electro-magnetic Pulse.
- Aluminum Casing: It implements the principle of Faraday's Cage to protect the target circuitry.

3.2 Protection from EMP attacks

Cars can be difficult to defend against EMP assaults because they include various electrical components that are susceptible to electromagnetic pulses. However, there are a few steps you may do to potentially boost your car's resistance against EMP effects:

Grounding: Check to see if your vehicle's electrical system is correctly grounded. A strong ground connection can aid in the diversion and dissipation of energy from an EMP.

Faraday Cage: Consider placing a Faraday cage around your vehicle's electronic components. A Faraday cage is a conductive container that can block electromagnetic fields. It serves as a barrier, shielding the electronics within from EMP impacts.

Shielding: Use more shielding to safeguard sensitive components. This might include putting metal shielding or insulation around crucial elements like the engine control unit (ECU) or ignition system to protect them from EMP radiation.

Surge protectors or transient voltage suppressors should be installed on your vehicle's electrical system. These devices may absorb and reroute excess electricity created by EMP occurrences, potentially saving sensitive equipment.

It is crucial to remember that while these techniques provide protection, they can ensure immunity from EMP impacts, but to certain extent only. The success of the safeguards will be determined on the magnitude and vicinity of the EMP event, as well as the unique vulnerabilities of your vehicle's electronics.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that the chance of a broad, high-altitude EMP strike is limited. While considering prospective dangers is wise, it is also vital to focus on more usual concerns, such as proper vehicle maintenance, effective security practices, and being prepared for other doomsday crises.

3.3 Faraday's Cage

A Faraday Cage operates to protect an object or series of contents from stray electromagnetic waves. This is done by placing an electromagnetic-sensitive device inside a container constructed of conductive metal.

Figure 4. Faraday's Cage

In the presence of an external electric field, the charges within the conductive material of the Faraday Cage redistribute themselves appropriately under the effect of the external field. The then rearranged charges induce an electric field in directional opposition to the applied external field, negating its magnitude. The net impact is an electromagnetically-neutral volume of the Faraday Cage.

Construction of a Faraday Cage requires several materials. The quality and magnitude of such materials will vary depending on the intent of the established Faraday Cage. A sealable container must be appropriately chosen such that it may fully contain the desired contents of the Faraday Cage. Minor Inconsistencies in the shape and structure of the container are acceptable as the container will be sheltered in conductive material. A conductive material with the capability of surrounding the determined container is also necessary.

Figure 5. Cylindrical Faraday's Cage

The electromagnetic characteristics of the conductive material are only required to be capable of carrying charges while under the presence of a field of specified magnitude. To this end, Silver is one of the most conductive materials available, but can be quite costly. Aluminum is much more accessible and manages sufficient conductivity. Under the presence of an external electric field, charges become redistributed throughout the conductive material so that like charges are pushed away from the source of the electric field, while opposite charges are attracted. In this way, charges are separated so that they form an electric field in opposition to the applied one.

3.4 High Voltage Generator

Figure 6. High Voltage ARC Generator gap Circuit

Input Voltage (V)	3.3V ~ 5V DC
Max. Operating Current (A)	2 – 5
Max. Output Voltage	1600 V
Max. Output Current (A)	0.5 A
Discharge Time	10s

3.5 Tools

HARDWARE:

- High Voltage Generator
- Faraday’s Cage

• Copper Coil

- SOFTWARE:**
- Multisim

3.6 Testing Circuit

We have designed a testing circuit to demonstrate the concept and provide a proof that the high voltage generator being used in the EMP generation circuit is capable enough of producing 1600V across the circuit.

Figure 7. Test Circuit

We have used 10 resistors of 100k ohm each. Connected a Li-ion battery to power up the circuit.

Connected a high voltage generator across the circuit and its action is regulated using a switch.

Figure 8. Side view of the circuit

3.6.1 Observations

Figure 9. Voltage Measurement-1

In the 1st measurement of the voltage across the 100k ohm resistor is found to be 126V. The negative sign indicates the polarity of voltage.

Figure 10. Voltage Measurement-2

In the 2nd measurement of the voltage across the 100k ohm resistor is found to be 123V.

From the observed measurements, we can state that the voltage across each resistor is in the range of 123V to 126V at any point of time.

Figure 11. Virtual representation of the circuit

Using the voltage divider concept, it can be stated that the voltage across each resistor will be equal to the total voltage divided by the total number of resistors, irrespective of the resistance of the resistors.

The above statement can be formulated as:

Voltage across each resistor = (Total voltage) / (Total number of resistors)

So, from the observations made above, we can see that voltage across each resistor is around 125V, which results in the total voltage across the circuit to be ~1250V, which lies in the range of the specification of the high voltage generator (1600V).

This phenomenon is possible because, the current is observed only in milliamperes(mA).

Figure 12. Current measurement

In the measurement of the current across the 100k ohm resistor is found to be 1.5mA.

Since, the current generated is 1.5mA, it is safe and the wires can withstand the voltage being produced.

3.7 Prototype

Figure 13. Top View

Figure 14. Bottom View

3.7.1 Working

In the hardware prototype of EMP generation circuit, we have used-

- Li-ion batteries
- High Voltage Generators
- Connecting wires
- Copper insulated wires for coils
- Switch

The batteries provide input of 3.75V, to the high voltage generators, which further produces an output voltage of ~1250V across the circuit, and a current of 1.5mA. This is possible because highvoltage generator is comprised of cascaded transformers inside the circuitry, which allows to produce very high voltage, while keeping the current to the minimum, across the terminals.

The copper insulated wires are made up into coils of 6 turns each which facilitates the EMP to getinduced radially outward.

The switch is connected across the positive terminals of the batteries to the positive terminals of the high voltage generators and the negative terminal of the batteries to the negative terminals of high voltage generators, to manually regulate the flow of charges across the spark gap in the circuit.

Figure 15. Full View of the prototype

The entire model, consists of 4 coils from each side of the block to increase the overall intensity and area of impact, of the EMP getting induced.

Since the coils are placed in the same plane, the EMP waves produced by each individual coil will not interfere with other coils, thus resulting in the direction the EMP waves in radially outward direction.

The spark gap is made between the terminal of high voltage generator and the coil. This acts as a capacitor which can rapidly charge and discharge to produce surges of EMP waves when turned on. The metal screws improve the conductivity and provide better transmission of spark across the terminals.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Device without EMP protection

Figure 16. Sample data provided to device without Faraday's cage

Figure 17. Data reset due to outburst of EMP waves generated by the coil

4.2 Device with EMP protection

Figure 18. Result-1

Figure 19. Result-2

Figure 20. Sample data provided to device placed inside Faraday's Cage

Figure 21. Device did not reset because outburst of EMP waves generated by the coil was grounded by the Faraday's Cage

4.3 List of Devices affected by EMP attack

List of Devices	E1 (low-altitude burst)	E2 (high-altitude burst)	E3 (geomagnetic disturbance)
Communications systems (cellular, satellite, microwave)	✓	✓	
Power grid components (transformers, power lines)	✓	✓	
Navigation systems (GPS, radar)	✓	✓	
Automobiles (engine control systems)	✓	✓	
Additional power grid components (substations, generators)		✓	
Financial systems (ATMs, electronic funds transfer)		✓	
Emergency response systems (911, police/fire radios)		✓	
Power plants, large transformers	✓	✓	✓
Industrial control systems (chemical plants, oil refineries)	✓	✓	✓
Additional navigation systems (aircraft, ships)	✓	✓	✓

Table 4.1: List of Devices affected by EMP attack

The effects of an EMP on specific devices will depend on a variety of factors including the strength of the EMP, the design and shielding of the device, and the susceptibility of the specific component within the device.

4.4 Engine Control Unit (ECU)

The Engine Control Unit (ECU), also known as the Engine Control Module (ECM), is a critical component in modern automobiles. It is an electronic control unit that manages and regulates various functions related to the engine's operation, performance, and emissions. The ECU monitors sensor inputs and controls the actuators to ensure optimal engine performance and efficiency.

Overall Function:

The ECU acts as the brain of the engine management system. It continuously receives inputs from various sensors, such as the throttle position sensor, oxygen sensor, crankshaft position sensor, and coolant temperature sensor. Based on these inputs, the ECU processes the data, makes calculations, and determines the appropriate outputs for actuators like fuel injectors, ignition coils, and idle control valves. It ensures that the engine operates within specified parameters for fuel delivery, ignition timing, air-fuel ratio, and other factors, aiming for optimal performance, fuel efficiency, and emissions control.

ECU Components:

The ECU is typically a small box-shaped module with multiple electrical connectors. It contains a microcontroller, memory, and input/output circuits. The microcontroller, often a specialized microprocessor, performs the calculations and controls the ECU's functions. The memory stores various maps, tables, and algorithms used for calculations and adjustments.

Sensor Inputs:

Sensors placed throughout the engine and exhaust system provide vital data to the ECU. These sensors measure parameters like engine speed, throttle position, airflow, coolant temperature, oxygen levels in the exhaust, and more. The ECU continuously reads these sensor inputs to monitor the engine's operating conditions and make necessary adjustments.

Actuator Outputs:

Based on the sensor inputs and internal programming, the ECU controls various actuators to influence engine operations. For example, it adjusts the fuel injectors to regulate the amount of fuel injected into the combustion chambers, controls the ignition timing to optimize combustion, and modulates the idle control valve to maintain a stable idle speed. The ECU sends electrical signals to

these actuators, commanding them to perform specific actions.

Figure 22. ECM of Tata Nano

Figure 23. Internal circuitry of the ECM

Figure 24. Power/ Data socket of ECM

Figure 25. Bottom view of ECM

Figure 26. ECU in the Faraday cage- protected from the EMP attack

The ECM is shielded within a Faraday cage, safeguarding it against potential damage from electromagnetic pulse (EMP) attacks. The Faraday cage acts as a protective barrier, blocking external electromagnetic waves and preventing them from interfering with or damaging the sensitive electronics inside the ECM.

4.4.1 ECM Diagnostic Reports

Figure 27. ECU healthy diagnostic report

The diagnostic report provides a clear demonstration of the ECM's performance both before and after being placed inside the Faraday cage during exposure to EMP waves. The report confirms that the ECM remains in a fully functional state. This conclusion is drawn from the fact that the diagnostic system successfully recognizes the statuscodes and displays the Diagnostic Trouble Codes (DTCs). The visibility of the DTCs indicates thatthe ECM is actively monitoring and detecting any faults or issues within the vehicle systems. Thepresence of recognized status codes further supports the assertion that the ECM remains operational and unaffected by the EMP waves due to the protection provided by the Faraday cage.

Figure 28. Live parameters-1

Figure 29. Live parameters-2

The ECU has undergone thorough testing using an ECU scanner that utilizes live engine parameters. This testing methodology allows for real-time monitoring and analysis of crucial engine parameters, providing accurate insights into the ECU's performance and enabling effective diagnostics and troubleshooting of engine-related issues.

Pre-Repair

Vehicle Diagnostic Report

Repair Shop

Shop Name:
 Address:
 Zip Code:
 Telephone:
 Email:
 SN:989510040804
 Test Time:2023-05-19 23:47:06
 Technician Name:Gsgs

Vehicle Information

Make:Tata
 Model: tata nano
 VIN:MEE#####553
 Odometer:30871 km
 Vehicle Software Version:V43.65
 Diagnostic Application Version:V6.00.003
 Diagnostic path:Automatically Search

System fault code

The following system is abnormal:

ECM (Engine Control Module) 2 problems exist

1.DTC012029 Throttle Potentiometer Circuit Track 1,Signal Incoherence.	Active
2.DTC022029 Throttle Potentiometer Circuit Track 2,Signal Incoherence.	Active

The following systems are OK:

- 1.IC (Instrument Cluster)
- 2.UCH
- 3.SRS (Supplemental Inflatable Restraint System)
- 4.Radio

Figure 30. ECU diagnostic report with DTC (Diagnostic Trouble Code)

This comprehensive report showcases the ECM's diagnosis conducted using live parameters of the vehicle. By analyzing real-time data from the car's various systems, the report provides valuable insights into the ECM's functionality and highlights any potential issues or faults for effective troubleshooting and maintenance.

Figure 31. EMP attack on ECM of the car

Following the EMP attack on the ECU, the ECU scanner failed to recognize and retrieve data from the damaged ECU. The impact of the EMP resulted in the loss of functionality and communication between the ECU and the scanner. Specifically, when attempting to diagnose the ECU of a Tata Nano, manufactured by Bosch, the scanner was unable to establish a connection or read any information from the affected ECU. This highlights the severe consequences of an EMP attack on electronic systems, such as the ECU, rendering them non-functional and requiring extensive repairs or replacement to restore proper operation.

4.4.2 ECM Scanner:

An Engine Control Module (ECM) scanner, also known as an OBD-II scanner or diagnostic tool, is a device used to interface with the ECM of a vehicle for diagnostic and troubleshooting purposes. Here are some key points about ECM scanners:

Function: An ECM scanner allows users to communicate with the vehicle's ECM to retrieve information, diagnose problems, and monitor various parameters related to the engine and other vehicle systems.

On-Board Diagnostics (OBD): ECM scanners comply with OBD standards, such as OBD-II, which is a standardized system implemented in most vehicles since the 1990s. OBD-II scanners can access and interpret diagnostic trouble codes (DTCs) generated by the ECM.

DTC Retrieval: ECM scanners can read and display DTCs stored in the ECM's memory. DTCs are specific codes that indicate issues or faults detected by the ECM in various vehicle systems, such as the engine, transmission, emissions, and more.

Live Data Monitoring: ECM scanners can display real-time data from various sensors and modules connected to the ECM. This includes parameters such as engine RPM, coolant temperature, oxygen sensor readings, fuel trim levels, and more. Live data monitoring helps diagnose intermittent issues and monitor system performance.

Freeze Frame Data: Some ECM scanners can retrieve freeze frame data, which captures the snapshot of vehicle sensor data at the time a DTC is triggered. This information provides additional context to diagnose the cause of a particular fault.

Clearing DTCs: ECM scanners allow users to clear stored DTCs from the ECM's memory after addressing the underlying issues. Clearing DTCs resets the vehicle's MIL (Malfunction Indicator Lamp) or check engine light.

Advanced Functions: Higher-end ECM scanners may offer advanced features like bi-directional control, allowing users to send commands to the ECM for specific tests or actuate components like fuel injectors, solenoids, or valves. This facilitates advanced diagnostics, system testing, and reprogramming capabilities.

Connectivity: ECM scanners can connect to the vehicle's ECM using various methods, including a physical cable connection (e.g., OBD-II ports) or wireless interfaces such as Bluetooth or Wi-Fi. Some scanners may require additional software or mobile apps to interface with the ECM.

Compatibility: ECM scanners are designed to work with specific vehicle makes, models, and model years. It's important to ensure that the scanner is compatible with the vehicle's ECM and supports the necessary communication protocols.

User Interface: ECM scanners feature an interface, typically a screen or display, to view and navigate through the retrieved data, select functions, and perform diagnostic operations. Some scanners have built-in buttons or touchscreens for user interaction.

ECM scanners are essential tools for automotive technicians, mechanics, and vehicle owners, providing valuable insights into the vehicle's condition, aiding in troubleshooting, and enabling effective repairs.

Figure 32. Failed ECM diagnosis

We can observe from the above diagnostic ECM scan, the OBD (On-Board Diagnostics) was not working, due to the interference with EMP waves.

The canbus protocol, PWM protocol and the VPW protocol have been failed after the EMP attack.

Figure 33. Tata nano ECM scan

The on-board diagnosis (OBD) using the ECU scanner in a simulated approach, by selecting the car model (Tata Nano), and perform Engine management scan.

Figure 34. Failure of EMS (Engine Management Scan) in the ECM

After the direct exposure of ECM to the EMP waves, the logical devices such as the microcontroller TC1762 have been wiped out and there is the occurrence of fallacy in the performance parameters.

A comprehensive experiment was conducted wherein various electronic devices, including mobilephones, mice, calculators, and remotes, were subjected to a similar EMP attack to highlight the profound impact on electronic gadgets. The results showcased the grave consequences of EMP on these devices containing processors and integrated circuits. Following the EMP exposure, all the tested electronic gadgets experienced severe malfunctions and failures. Mobile phones lost network connectivity, mouse and calculators became unresponsive, and remotes ceased to function entirely. This experiment serves as a stark reminder of the vulnerability of electronic devices to EMP events, emphasizing the urgent need for protective measures and robust designs to mitigate the potential devastating effects of such attacks.

Figure 35. EMP on mobile phone

Figure 36. Phone in faradays cage- protected from EMP

The figure illustrates the repercussions of EMP waves on a mobile phone. The visual shows a distorted display, indicating the immediate impact of the electromagnetic pulse. Additionally, the partial wipeout of the internal circuitry logic is apparent, leading to malfunctioning or non-functional components. The critical observation made is that prolonged exposure to EMP waves would result in the permanent destruction of semiconductor logical devices within the mobile phone. This emphasizes the detrimental nature of EMP attacks on electronic devices, particularly mobile phones, and emphasizes the urgency of implementing protective measures and resilient designs to withstand the long-term damage caused by such electromagnetic disturbances. The figure represents the protection of the mobile phone using a Faradays cage. The EMP waves have been grounded successfully, resulting in the protection of the device. The System On-Chip (SOC) processor is the Infineon TC1762, which has the following pinout

Figure 37. TC1762 Pin configuration

On-Chip Memories:

As shown in the TC1762 block diagram, some of the TC1762 units provide on-chip memories that are used as program or data memory.

- Program memory in PMU
 - 16 Kbyte Boot ROM (BROM)
 - 1024 Kbyte Program Flash (PFlash)
- Program memory in PMI
 - 8 Kbyte Scratch-Pad RAM (SPRAM)
 - 8 Kbyte Instruction Cache (ICACHE)
- Data memory in PMU
 - 16 Kbyte Data Flash (DFlash)
 - 4 Kbyte Overlay RAM (OVRAM)
- Data memory in DMI
 - 32 Kbyte Local Data RAM (LDRAM)
- On-chip SRAM with parity error protection

General Purpose Timer Array:

The GPTA provides a set of timers, compare, and capture functionalities that can be flexibly combined to form signal measurement and signal generation units. They are optimized for tasks typical of engine, gearbox, electrical motor control applications, but can also be used to generate simple and complex signal waveforms needed in other industrial applications.

Figure 38. Logical representation of TC1762

The logical block diagram of the Infineon TC1762 microcontroller can be described as follows:

TriCore CPU Cores: The TC1762 features three TriCore CPU cores, denoted as CPU1, CPU2, and CPU3. These cores are responsible for executing instructions and performing computational tasks.

1. **Memory Interface:** This component manages the interaction between the CPU cores and the various types of memory used in the microcontroller, such as program memory (Flash) and data memory (RAM).
2. **Flash Memory:** The Flash memory is used for storing the program code that is executed by the CPU cores. It provides non-volatile storage and is typically used for firmware and program code storage.
3. **RAM (Data Memory):** The RAM is used for storing data during program execution. It provides temporary storage for variables, stack space, and other data used by the CPU cores.
4. **Peripherals:** The TC1762 includes a range of integrated peripherals to support various automotive applications. These peripherals may include:
 - a. **Communication Interfaces:** Serial communication interfaces such as CAN (Controller Area Network), LIN (Local Interconnect Network), and UART (Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter) for communication with other devices or systems.
 - b. **Timers:** Various timers and counters for generating precise timing signals, measuring time intervals, and performing tasks like PWM (Pulse Width Modulation).
 - c. **Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC):** An ADC for converting analog signals into digital data. It allows the microcontroller to interface with analog sensors or signals.
 - d. **Digital I/O:** General-purpose digital input/output pins for interfacing with external devices or sensors.
 - e. **Interrupt Controller:** Manages the interrupt signals generated by various sources, allowing the microcontroller to respond to time-critical events or external stimuli.
5. **Bus Matrix:** The bus matrix facilitates communication and data transfer between different modules and peripherals within the microcontroller. It manages data flow and arbitration between multiple bus masters.
6. **Power Management:** This component manages power supply and power modes of the microcontroller, allowing for efficient power consumption and control.
7. **Debug and Trace:** The TC1762 may include features for debugging and tracing program execution, such as on-chip debug interfaces or trace ports.

Figure 39. Terminal diagram of TC176

V. CONCLUSION

- The main aim of the project focuses on developing an EMP proof car, which can withstand a large scale EMP attack (E1, E2) level. The proposed invention uses principles of Faraday cage and protects the electronic components in a car which are more susceptible to EMP attacks.
- Most electronic protection devices will be destroyed by High electrostatic gradient. The gradient can be high enough to destroy semiconductors directly where the gradient across a semiconductor junction is higher than the absolute max survivable. A Faraday cage will stop this.
- The ECM (Engine Control Module) controls specific parts of the engine, regulating and sending commands. While the PCM (Powertrain Control Module) is used in newer models to control almost all engine functions.
- The best EMP protection is a combination of protection devices, Faraday cage, and magnetic shield.

5.2 Future Scope

- EMP Proofing the cars on large scale and making it feasible for the common man.
- EMP shielding technology on satellites and required environments.
- Protecting Army & Military Cantonments with EMP proof technology.

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